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endometrial hyperplastic processes, hyperplasia, chronic inflammation, pathological process, precancer, signs of tissue change.

Relevance. A number of studies have noted a high degree of hereditary burden in such patients for the development of tumor diseases of the genital organs, which is an important factor in the development of endometrial pathology [7, 9, 10]. An analysis of reproductive function revealed a significantly high incidence of infertility in patients with AGE (33.3%) and uterine body cancer - 68% ($p < 0.05$). Other researchers also point to impaired reproductive function in such patients [2, 7, 8, 12]. In the work of I. Savelli, AH was singled out as one of the leading risk factors (RF) for the development of HPE. The incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2) also naturally increased from group 1 (0%) to group 6 (13.6%) ($p < 0.05$). DM as a risk factor for the occurrence of hyperplastic and malignant endometrial

ENDOMETRIUM AND ITS HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

Hyperplastic processes of the endometrium is one of the most urgent problems of gynecology due to the high frequency of occurrence (in the structure of gynecological morbidity - from 30 to 55%), the possibility of recurrence and malignancy [2, 5, 6, 8]. The issues of oncological transformation of the endometrium in patients of reproductive age are especially significant in connection with the upcoming implementation of the reproductive function [1, 11]. The study included 100 patients (mean age 34.7 ± 3.2 years) who applied to the gynecological hospital during 2019-2021. Retrospectively, all patients were divided into 6 groups depending on the morphological type of the pathological process of the endometrium.

processes has been noted by many researchers [6, 7, 12]. The combination of uterine fibroids and adenomyosis was significantly higher in the group of patients with complex hyperplasia without atypia (8.7%), atypical hyperplasia (14.3%) and uterine body cancer (18.2%) ($p < 0.05$), which, possibly due to the mutually stimulating influence of pathological processes in the endo- and myometrium. Many researchers pay attention to the frequent combination of HPE and polyps with uterine myoma (29–96%) and endometriosis (25–69%) [4, 5, 9]. PCOS was more common in patients with HPE (group 3 - 7.0%, group 4 - 8.7%) and was significantly more common in groups with AHE and EC (11.9 and 18.2%, respectively; $p < 0.05$), which once again emphasizes the need to classify PCOS as a

significant risk factor for the development of malignant pathology of the endometrium [6, 7, 11].

Purpose of the study: To study the structure of endometrial hyperplastic processes.

Materials and methods of research. The patients were divided into 6 groups: group 1 included patients with chronic endometritis (CE) (n=20), group 2 - with endometrial polyp (n=20), group 3 - with simple endometrial hyperplasia without atypia (n=20), in the 4th - with complex endometrial hyperplasia without atypia (n=20), in the 5th - with complex endometrial hyperplasia with atypia (n=10), in the 6th - with highly differentiated endometrial adenocarcinoma Stage I (n=10). Patients with simple hyperplasia and atypia were not included in the study. We carried out a detailed comparative analysis of clinical, anamnestic and diagnostic parameters in patients of the formed groups. The study of hereditary burden revealed a significant (more than 3 times) increase in susceptibility to tumor processes in patients with atypical endometrial hyperplasia (40%) and highly differentiated endometrial adenocarcinoma (59%) compared with the groups of CE (15%) and hyperplasia without atypia - 19 % (p<0.05).

Results: In our study, the incidence of endometrial hyperplasia in history was significantly higher in the 5th (10%; p<0.05) and 6th groups (30%; p<0.05), and the frequency of recurrence of endometrial polyps was significantly higher in the 2nd th group (20%; p<0.05), which indicates the resistance of these processes to previous therapy in this category of patients [7, 9].

In the patients examined by us, as a concomitant pathology, arterial hypertension (AH) was the most common, manifested by hypertension or vegetative-vascular dystonia of the hypertensive type. Moreover, the frequency of this pathology increased from the 1st (5%) to the 6th (20%) group (p<0.05) and was significantly higher in the 5th (20%) and 6th (30%) groups (p<0.05). In the study of body mass index (BMI), we noted a persistent trend towards its increase from the 1st (BMI 22.5±1.3) to group 6 (BMI 31±2.4; p<0.05). In our studies, the use of color Doppler ultrasound (CDO) was the main method of non-invasive diagnostics. There was no statistical difference in benign diseases. Only in the malignant process was a sharp increase in blood flow velocity in the arcuate arteries (Vmax - 0.34±0.08 m/s, Vmin - 0.18±0.1 m/s; p<0.05). The most informative was the study of the resistance index (RI), which also statistically differed from that in malignant processes (0.3±0.03; p<0.05). In our study, a statistically significant indicator of pronounced blood flow occurred in malignant lesions of the uterus, which is consistent with the data of other authors indicating low IR and pronounced blood flow in the endometrium as a marker of a malignant process. To study the molecular biological features of the pathogenesis of pathological processes in the endometrium, the frequency of abnormal methylation of the tumor growth suppressor genes MLH1, RASSF1, GSTP1, P16, RAR-b, CDX1 in biopsy samples of the endometrium in 100 patients was determined. In the analysis of gene methylation, sectional material of normal endometrium (n=7) served as a control, in

which no methylation of the studied genes was observed in any of the observations. After determining the average rate of abnormal gene methylation by groups, we found that the frequency of epigenomic disorders increases in the series: chronic endometritis (0.32%) → simple endometrial hyperplasia without atypia (3.1%) → complex endometrial hyperplasia without atypia (8.33 %) → endometrial polyp (9.67%) → complex endometrial hyperplasia with atypia (23.41%) → endometrial cancer (75.7%) ($p < 0.005$). The Katz method was used to assess the relative risk (RR) of developing oncopathology for each diagnostic factor. After establishing the main risk factors using the Pearson test, their correlation with each other was determined. The absence of a strong correlation between the signs and the presence of different combinations of clinical data made it possible to use the above clinical and anamnestic indicators as risk factors for the development of endometrial oncopathology.

We formed 3 groups of patients: with a low probability of developing cancer ($p = 0-0.29$), with a moderate one ($p = 0.3-0.59$), and with a high one ($p = 0.6-1.0$). The model was tested on patients of the 1st and 6th groups ($n = 54$). The sensitivity of the proposed model was 98%, the specificity was 92%. After 6 months of treatment, in no case was there a recurrence or progression of the pathological process of the endometrium. In the 1st group, a low probability of developing cancer was determined in 13 patients, moderate - in 4, high - in 3. Patients with CE from the high-risk group, in addition to basic antibiotic therapy, taking into account the pathogen, immunomodulatory, metabolic and

enzyme therapy, received progestogens in 2 -th phase of the cycle for 6 months. Control examination (ultrasound, pipel biopsy) revealed no pathology. In the 2nd group, a low probability of developing cancer was determined in 12 patients, moderate - in 4, high - in 4. One patient of the 2nd group with a high risk of developing uterine body cancer was treated with gonadotropic releasing hormone (GnRH) agonists. The control study (ultrasound with color doppler, Doppler) revealed no pathology. Three patients from the high-risk group received progestogen therapy in the 2nd phase of the cycle. During the control examination (ultrasound, curettage of the uterus), a recurrence of the polyp was found in all of them, and in 1 case an adenomatous component was detected in the polyp. In the 3rd group, a low probability of developing cancer was determined in 10 patients, moderate - in 8, high - in 2. Patients with a high risk of developing cancer of the uterine body received therapy with gestagens ($n = 2$) or GnRH agonists ($n = 3$). The control examination revealed no pathology of the endometrium. Four patients were treated according to the standard scheme (gestagens in the 2nd phase of the cycle). During the control examination, a recurrence of simple endometrial hyperplasia was found in 2 patients, a transition to complex hyperplasia in 1, and atypical endometrial hyperplasia was found in 1 morphological study. In the 4th group, a low probability of developing cancer was determined in 11 patients, moderate - in 3, high - in 6. In the high-risk group, 1 patient was treated with progestogens, and 4 were treated with GnRH agonists. A control study did not reveal endometrial pathology. Six patients

received treatment according to the usual scheme (medroxyprogesterone - 200 mg on the 14th and 21st days of the cycle). In the control study, 3 patients had a recurrence of complex hyperplasia and 3 had the development of AHE. In the 5th group, a low probability of developing cancer was determined in 2 patients, moderate - in 3, high - in 5. Five patients from the high-risk group with realized reproductive function underwent hysterectomy. Morphological examination confirmed the diagnosis of AHE in 3 patients, and foci of highly differentiated endometrial adenocarcinoma were found in 2 patients. Three high-risk patients with AHE who refused surgical treatment were treated with gestagens for economic reasons. During the control curettage, 2 patients had a recurrence of AHE, 1 had the development of endometrial adenocarcinoma; 1 patient was treated with GnRH agonists. Control curettage

revealed a recurrence of AHE. Considering the high risk of AHE malignancy and taking into account the persistent desire of the patients to preserve the uterus, ablation of the endometrium followed by hormone therapy was performed in 7 patients. In our study, 3 patients received gestagens after ablation, 4 patients received GnRH agonists. During the control examination (ultrasound with color doppler and Doppler) no pathology of the endometrium was found.

Conclusion. Thus, the need to develop a mathematical model for predicting the risk of developing endometrial oncopathology using binary logistic regression allows for a differentiated and evidence-based approach to the tactics of managing patients of reproductive age with pathological processes of the endometrium, the need for its development and implementation in practical medicine is one of the topical issues today.

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